

Field Guide to Mangroves of Belen, Calabanga

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Mangroves in Belen, Calabanga, Camarines Sur listed by family

TRUE MANGROVES					
Family	Scientific Name	Local Names	Conservation Status		
			IUCN Global	DAO 2017-11	CITES
Acanthaceae	<i>Acanthus ebracteatus</i> Vahl	lagiwliw, ragoyroy	LC	OWS	NL
	<i>Acanthus volubilis</i> Wall.	lagiwliw, ragoyroy	LC	OWS	NL
	<i>Avicennia marina</i> (Forssk.) Vierh.	bungalon, apiapi, miapi, bayabason	LC	OWS	NL
	<i>Avicennia marina</i> var. <i>rumphiana</i> (Hallier fil.) Bakh. (formerly <i>A. rumphiana</i>)	bungalon, apiapi, miapi, kuyapi	VU	OWS	NL
Arecaceae	<i>Nypa fruticans</i> Wurmb	sapsap, sasa, nipa	LC	OWS	NL
Euphorbiaceae	<i>Excoecaria agallocha</i> L.	buta-buta, lipata, alipata	LC	OWS	NL
Lythraceae	<i>Sonneratia alba</i> Sm.	pagatpat	LC	OWS	NL
Meliaceae	<i>Xylocarpus granatum</i> J.Koenig	tabigi, tambigi	LC	OWS	NL
Primulaceae	<i>Aegiceras corniculatum</i> (L.) Blanco	tayokan, kawilan, saging-saging, tinduk-tindukan	LC	OWS	NL
	<i>Aegiceras floridum</i> Roem. & Schult.	katuganung, kwasay, saging-saging, tinduk-tindukan	NT	OWS	NL
Rhizophoraceae	<i>Bruguiera cylindrica</i> (L.) Blume	pototan, busain	LC	OWS	NL
	<i>Bruguiera gymnorhiza</i> (L.) Lam.	pototan, busain, bakhaw	LC	OWS	NL
	<i>Ceriops zippeliana</i> Blume	baras-baras, lapis-lapis, malatungal	LC	OWS	NL
	<i>Rhizophora apiculata</i> Blume	bakhaw, bulubaladaw, bakhaw lalaki	LC	OWS	NL
	<i>Rhizophora mucronata</i> Lam.	bakhaw, bakhaw babae	LC	OWS	NL
Rubiaceae	<i>Scyphiphora hydrophylacea</i> C.F.Gaertn.	bolaling, sagasa, nilad, hanbulali	LC	OWS	NL
MANGROVE ASSOCIATES					
Malvaceae	<i>Brownlowia tersa</i> (L.) Kosterm.	maragomon	NT	OWS	NL
Pteridaceae	<i>Acrostichum speciosum</i> Willd.	Palaypay, lagolo	LC	OWS	NL

Legend:
IUCN – LC (Least Concern); NT (Near Threatened); VU (Vulnerable) | **DAO 2017-11** – OWS (non-threatened; other wildlife species) | **CITES** – NL (Not Listed)

How to read this guide?

Scientific name
Local name(s)
Taxonomic family

***Excoecaria agallocha* L.**

Local name: buta-buta, lipata, alipata

FAMILY EUPHORBIACEAE

IUCN Global Conservation Status

FL	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D
FR	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D

Phenological Calendar
FL – flowering
FR – fruiting

Photos of the different diagnostic key features used to identify the mangroves

Acanthus ebracteatus Vahl

Local name: lagiwliw, ragoyroy

FAMILY ACANTHACEAE

FL	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D
FR	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D

Acanthus volubilis Wall

Local name: lagiwliw, ragoyroy

FAMILY ACANTHACEAE

FL	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D
FR	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D

Aegiceras corniculatum (L.) Blanco

Local name: tayokan, kawilan, saging-saging, tinduk-tindukan

FAMILY PRIMULACEAE

FL	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D
FR	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D

Aegiceras floridum Roem. & Schult.

Local name: katuganung, kwasay, saging-saging, tinduk-tindukan

FAMILY PRIMULACEAE

FL	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D
FR	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D

Avicennia marina (Forssk.) Vierh.

Local name: bungalon, apiapi, miapi, bayabason

FAMILY ACANTHACEAE

FL	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D
FR	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D

Avicennia marina var. *rumphiana* (Hallier fil.) Bakh.

Local name: bungalon, apiapi, miapi, kuyapi

FAMILY ACANTHACEAE

FL	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D
FR	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D

Bruguiera cylindrica (L.) Blume

Local name: pototan, busain

FAMILY RHIZOPHORACEAE

FL	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D
FR	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D

Bruguiera gymnorhiza (L.) Lam.

Local name: pototan, busain, bakhaw

FAMILY RHIZOPHORACEAE

FL	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D
FR	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D

Ceriops zippeliana Blume

Local name: baras-baras, lapis-lapis, malatungal

FAMILY RHIZOPHORACEAE

FL	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D
FR	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D

Excoecaria agallocha L.

Local name: buta-buta, lipata, alipata

FAMILY EUPHORBIACEAE

FL	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D
FR	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D

Nypa fruticans Wurmbe

Local name: sapsap, sasa, nipa

FAMILY ARECACEAE

FL	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D
FR	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D

Rhizophora apiculata Blume

Local name: bakhaw, bulubaladaw, bakhaw lalaki

FAMILY RHIZOPHORACEAE

FL	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D
FR	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D

Rhizophora mucronata Lam.

Local name: bakhaw, bakhaw babae

FAMILY RHIZOPHORACEAE

FL	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D
FR	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D

Scyphiphora hydrophylacea C.F.Gaertn.

Local name: bolaling, sagasa, nilad, hanbulali

FAMILY RUBIACEAE

FL	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D
FR	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D

Sonneratia alba Sm.

Local name: pagatpat

FAMILY LYTHRACEAE

FL	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D
FR	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D

Xylocarpus granatum J.Koenig

Local name: tabigi, tambigi

FAMILY MELIACEAE

FL	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D
FR	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D

MANGROVE ASSOCIATES

Acrostichum speciosum Willd.

Local name: Palaypay, lagolo

FAMILY PTERIDACEAE

Brownlowia tersa (L.) Kosterm.

Local name: maragomon

FAMILY MALVACEAE

Citation:

De Los Santos, A., Sese, J. Z., Declaro, M. S., Quiñones, D., Sagara, M. S., Flor, S. G., Parone, M., Reyes, J. J., Rosales, K. D., Masalunga, R., Bañega, M., Leonardo, M. F., Tamayo, G., Singson, G. P., Modino, L. J., Ramos, B. T., Pejo, C. L., & Nubla, F. M. Field Guide to Mangroves of Belen, Calabanga, Camarines Sur. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17072459>

Oscar M. Lopez Center
Science for Climate Resilient Communities

*"Mangroves are not just trees; they are our neighbors, our protectors, and our legacy.
To care for them is to care for our future."*

— Dr. Jurgenne H. Primavera, Filipino mangrove scientist & conservationist

